

The Relevance Of Aḍavu-s In Sanskrit Treatise ‘Saṅgīta Sāramṛta’ To The Contemporary Aḍavu-s Of Bharatanāṭya

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Abstract:

‘*Saṅgīta Sāramṛta*’ authored by Marata King Tulajaji – I of Tanjore written in the 18th century AD., names and describes 16 *Aḍavu-s*, which were done in *Sadir Natch*, the dance done during the period the treatise was written. This is the only available documentation on *Aḍavu-s*. The word *Aḍavu* and the names of many are found in two Tamil treatises and many Kannada poetic works but there is no description as to their execution.

Evolution of *Aḍavu* can be traced to *Karaṇa-s* of Bharata’s *Nāṭyaśāstra* and many *Dēsī* techniques which came into vogue after *Nāṭyaśāstra*. The current *Aḍavu-s* taught by the the Gurus of *Bhartanāṭya* are off shoot of the practicing traditions developed over many generations.

The paper is based on author’s MPhil dissertation “Tracing the *Aḍavu-s* through Dance Literature and Practicing Traditions” and PhD Thesis “Study of Influence of *Mārga Karaṇa-s* on *Aḍavu-s* from the perspective of Structure and Aesthetics”. The author video graphed *Aḍavu-s* being done in the eight *Bāni-s* of *Bharatanāṭya* at present, for her MPhil dissertation and studied them to see how many of them were similar to the description of *Aḍavu-s* mentioned in the treatise *Saṅgīta Sāramṛta*. It has been concluded that many of the *Aḍavu-s* that are described in the treatise, written around 300 years ago, are prevalent even today with small changes.

Keywords: Sangita Saramrita, Adavu, Contemporary Adavu, Sadir Nach, Bharatanatya Bāni

Introduction

According to eminent scholar R. Satyanarayana, “*Aḍavu* means the combined acts of *aṅga*¹ and *pratyāṅga*²; in ordinary parlance, it is a combination or sequence of the *nṛtta*³

¹ *Aṅga* - Main organ

² *Pratyāṅga* – Ancillary organ

³ *Nṛtta* – Dance done by the movements of the body parts

movements of hands and feet between successive *sthānakas*⁴. In this sense, therefore, the Aḍavu-s are the kinematic alphabets of Bharatanāṭyam.” (Satyanarayana 1959:136). The terminologies that are used in connection with Aḍavu as it is perceived today are many; such as meaning⁵, definition⁶, characteristic⁷, Bāni⁸ and many more. They have been taken as the basis to understand the relevance of Aḍavu-s documented in the Sanskrit Treatise *Saṅgīta Sārāmṛta* to the Contemporary Aḍavu-s of Bharatanāṭya.

Earliest historical reference:

The word Aḍavu has been traced to early Tamil literature of second century AD called *Kūttanūl* authored by Sātanār and the treatise placed between 9th – 13th AD, *Bharataseṇapatiam* authored by Adi vāyilār. *Kūttanūl* mentions Aḍavu-s and Aḍaivus in seven places. *Bharataseṇapatiam* mentions Aḍivu and *Tattaḍivu*; *Kattaḍaivuvu* in two places. However, there is no detailed description of how to execute them in any of these references. *Saṅgīta Sārāmṛta* names and describes with their *Sollukaṭṭus*,⁹ sixteen Aḍavu-s, which were done in *Sadir Nāṭch*, the dance done during the period the treatise was written. Padma Subrahmanyam says in her book “Bharata’s Art - Then and Now” that Aḍaivuvu was used for a whole sequence of *Nṛtta* similar to Aḍavu *Korvai*, meaning to link. This word Aḍaivuvu slowly got obliterated and only Aḍavu meaning basic unit of dance came to stay.

Recent trends & development

What was called as ‘Sadir’ or ‘Dāsi Nāṭyam’ from late 14th Century AD was later renamed *Bharatanāṭya* in the 20th century AD. “Sadir is a dance style, which is mainly based on the Aḍavu technique that emerged after 14th Century AD.” (Subramanyam 1979:77). The current paper is restricted to usage of Aḍavu-s in *Bharatanāṭya*. The special technique

⁴ *Sthānaka* – the still pose of the body from which movements of Aḍavu start

⁵ Meaning of Aḍavu – Aḍavu, meaning step is the basic unit of *Nṛtta*, the root of which is *Ādu* meaning to dance in all the four major south Indian languages.

⁶ Definition of Aḍavu – The rhythmic movement of the body involving the *Aṅgas* (main organs), *Pratyāṅgas* (ancillary organs which can be moved easily) and *Upāṅgas* (minor organs which are all in the head) of the body to a *Tāla* (time measure or meter).

⁷ Characteristics of Aḍavu – 1. *Sthānaka* (starting and ending stance or still pose of Aḍavu), 2. *Nṛtta Hasta* (decorative hand gesture held while doing the Aḍavu) 3. *Cāri* (leg movements done while executing the Aḍavu) & 4. *Hastakṣetra* (the area covered by the hands and legs while doing the Aḍavu).

⁸ Bāni – The special techniques developed to teach Aḍavu-s by different *Guru*, carried through successive generations, came to be known as Bāni or *Parampara* meaning succession, named after the village or place of the first *Guru*.

⁹ *Sollukaṭṭus* – the Jatis (syllables) woven together, set to a *Tāla* which is said orally by the *Natuvanar*(the person putting the cymbals during a dance performance)

developed to teach the *Aḍavu-s* which was carried from generation to generation came to be known as *Bāni* or *Parampara*, which means succession. Major *Bānis* or *Paramparas* i.e. Practicing Traditions of *Bharathanatyā*, which have evolved over the years are:

- Muguru, Mysore, Nanjanagudu and Kolar Parampara in Karnataka (old Mysore state)
- Pandanallur, Tanjore, Vazhavor, Kalakshetra *Bāni* in Tamil Nadu (old Madras state).

Saṅgīta Sāramṛta (Sanskrit) By Tulajaji I:

Tulajaji - I ruled in South India from 1728-1736, with Tanjore as the capital (Raghuraman 2014:170). He is credited with genre of compositions including Padas and dramas in different languages and his most important work in the field of music and dance was the Sanskrit Treatise '*Saṅgīta Sāramṛta*'. There are 14 chapters of this work, compiled from palm leaves and old manuscripts, by Pandit Subrahmanya Sastri, with explanation in English, where necessary. In his work, some of the key Sanskrit words that were missing in the old manuscript were left as it was. Missing text has been interpreted by taking the context of the whole verse in this paper. *Saṅgīta Sāramṛta* is a landmark treatise from the point of view of *Aḍavu-s* in dance, because for the first time, it documents the *Aḍavu-s* that were done in the practicing tradition of *Sadir* dance of that era. There are 16 *Aḍavu-s* named and described in the Chapter on dance called '*Nruthyaprakaranam*', which are of great significance. The equivalent names in Tamil and Telugu and the *Sollukaṭṭu* used in that period for many of the *Aḍavu-s* are also given, which is of great importance to study the journey of *Aḍavu-s* from the 18th Century to present day *Aḍavu* repertoire and the changes that have taken place on the way.

Works done

- "Bharatanatyam in Tamil Nadu (After AD 1200)", the book written by Dr. K Kalarani, mentions only the names of the *Aḍavu-s* in Sanskrit and their equivalent names in Tamil as mentioned in *Saṅgīta Sāramṛta* and has not elaborated on them (Kalarani R. 2004: 158).
- Dr. Padma Subramanyam in her work "Bharata's Art - Then and Now" mentions this treatise while discussing the evolution of modern *Aḍavu-s* through *Sadir Nach*.
- Dr. R. Sathynarayana in his book "*Bharatanāṭyam – A critical study*" mentions the *Aḍavu-s* of *Sangita Sāramṛta* as significant from the point of view of *Aḍavu-s* done today.

- Shrama Vidhi: An insight into Adavu codification of king Thulaja's *Saṅgīta Sarāmr̥ta*. A lecture Demonstration by Uma Nambudaripad Sathynarayan and Lakshmi Parthasarathy Athreya. Researched and reconstructed by the above two dancers. This was presented at Natya Kala Conference 2019 arranged by Sri Krishna Gana Sabha, Chennai.
- Dr. Manorama B.N. has discussed about the 16 Aḍavu-s in the treatise in the Kannada book 'Yaksha Marga Mukura' published in 2022.

Research questions

- What is the relevance of *Aḍavu* mentioned in Sanskrit Treatise *Saṅgīta Sāramṛta* to the Contemporary *Aḍavu-s* of *Bharatanāṭya*?

Hypothesis

- The *Aḍavu-s* documented in *Saṅgīta Sāramṛta* are from the *Sadir Natch*, which was prevalent during the writing of the treatise.
- The *Aḍavu-s* as described in the treatise are done in the *Bharatanāṭya* Contemporary *Aḍavu-s*.

Scope of study

Study of the *Aḍavu-s* described in *Saṅgīta Sāramṛta* to find out how many of Contemporary *Aḍavu-s* are off shoots of those described in the treatise.

Methodology

Methodology which has been followed is Qualitative since it is art, Descriptive, since *Aḍavu-s* in the treatise have been described in detail with the Analysis also involving detailed description. It is Historical since it has a time line covering more than three centuries. A detailed study of the *Aḍavu-s* mentioned in the treatise was taken up for study for M.Phil. Dissertation "Tracing the *Aḍavu-s* through Dance Literature and Practicing Traditions" of the first author, under her guide who is the second author. The *Aḍavu-s* done in each of the eight *Bānis* have been listed and videotaped for that work. The work was further continued in PhD, the topic of the thesis was "Study of the influence of *Mārga Karaṇa* on *Aḍavu* from the perspective of Structure and Aesthetics". The study in PhD also involved studying the *Dēsī* techniques described in 12 Sanskrit Treatises, which came after *Nāṭyaśāstra*, to establish the link from *Mārga Karaṇas*, through *Dēsī* techniques, *Saṅgīta Sāramṛta Aḍavu-s* and finally

examining the the *Aḍavu-s* presently being done in eight *Bānis of Bharatanāṭya*, which were videotaped, to show the evolution of the contemporary *Aḍavu-s* through the centuries. The present paper is based on those studies.

Limitation

In view of the fact that only one Senior Guru has been interviewed for each *Bāni*, the *Aḍavu-s* as practiced by that Guru has been used in the study. This, therefore, is limited to that particular Guru and there could be variations within the *Bāni* in a larger sense.

Analysis

The sixteen *Aḍavu-s* in *Saṅgīta Sārāmṛta* have been discussed below:

1. *Sama Kuṭṭanam: Taṭṭu Aḍavu*

Translation: To the sound of *Theyya Theyyi* done by the musical instrument (*Paatakai*), Hitting both the feet on the ground in *Suddha mandala (Ayata Sthanaka)* is called *Taṭṭadava*. This becomes *Samakuttanam* for example, when *Theyya Theyyi* is done in *Vilamba* and other speeds.

Analysis: This *Aḍavu*, starting from *Ardhamaṇḍala* or *Ayata* posture and stamping the feet to the ground to the *Sollukaṭṭu Theyya Theyyi* for the beat of *Tala* in *Vilamba* (slow), *Madhyama* (medium) and *Dr̥tta* (fast) speeds, matches with the way *Taṭṭu Aḍavu* is done today.

2. *Khanatpāḍakuṭṭanam: Meṭṭu Aḍavu*

Translation: Lifting the heels one after the other, beating with the foot (digging) one after the other, with hands in *Patāka* would become '*Khanatpāḍakuṭṭanam*'. This is *Kuṭṭadavu*.

Analysis: This *Aḍavu* going on toes with heels up when hitting is done by digging the toes into the ground matches *Meṭṭu Aḍavu*, which is done today. The information about the *Aḍavu* is not complete since after going on the toes if leg is not hit in *Taṭṭu*, the first leg movement is not completed and *meṭṭu* in the other leg cannot be done. No *Sollukaṭṭu* is mentioned for this *Aḍavu*.

3. *Pārsvakuṭṭanam: Nātaḍavu*

Translation: Placing the heels away from the feet along with hands in *Tripatāka*, if there is beating on the ground that becomes *Nattitaṭṭadava*. This is the sign of *Pārsvakuṭṭanam*. Example – *Thaim tathaiyya* and called *Nāti Taṭṭadavu*. If it is done by moving, observing the hitting (beat), it is called *Pārsvatkuṭṭana* by the knowledgeable experts (*Nāttitaṭṭadavu*).

Analysis: The description in the verse points towards *Nātaḍavu* done today, which is done in *Ālīda*¹⁰ and *Pratyālīda*¹¹ positions. The position of the leg on heels is called *Añcita*¹².

4. *Pādapārsvakuṭṭanam: Dhi di thai Aḍavu*

Translation: The beats of the feet are differentiated to the front then to the side; If there were to be respective differences incorporated in the hand movements; The beats of the feet to the sides, completing to the sound of *Dhi ti thai* with the circular motion (of the feet) is called *Pādapārsvakuṭṭanam*. That would be called as *Dhi ti thai Kuṭṭanam*.

Analysis: Description in the Verse is pointing towards side and obtuse angle *Nātaḍavu*, similar to *Dhi di thai Aḍavu*, the *sollu* said at present is also *Dhi di thai*, which is used in *Alaripu Nritta Bandha* to come forward since *Pārsvakuṭṭanam* has already been described as *Nātaḍavu*.

5. *Pādapārsvakuṭṭanam - with hands Salaya kai Sahita Dhi ti thai Aḍavu*.

Translation: *Dhi ti thai* Aḍavu with hands

Analysis: There is no Sloka or explanation given after the heading of the *Aḍavu*. “*Salaya* is very similar to *Ardhapatāka*, except that the thumb is kept straight in alignment with other fingers” (Subrahmanyam 2021 22). This could point to *Nātaḍavu* with *Salaya kai* (hand).

¹⁰ *Ālīda* – Sitting on right leg left leg is stretched on heels three feet away

¹¹ *Pratyālīda* – The opposite of *Ālīda*.

¹² *Añcita* – The feet on heels with the toes and sole arched upward.

6. *Digidigyādikuṭṭanam*: Circular movement done on toes in *Ardhamaṇḍala* (moving on *Meṭṭu* similar to *Vicyava Bhūcāri*¹³)

Translation: Here the *Pāda* (feet) are spread and hands are placed in *Tripataka*. Differences born ----- (missing text) are agreed upon by experts. Standing in *Ardhamaṇḍala* the front foot is moved on the ground with a circular movement and is called *Digidigyādikuṭṭanam*.

Analysis: There is missing text after feet are spread and hands are placed in *Tripataka*. It says in the treatise *Utpaddyante* (are born) --- *Bedha* (---- differences). Thought can be given if *Pada*' word meaning foot can be added before *Bedha* to mean *Pādabedha*¹⁴ which creates different movements of the legs as agreed upon by experts. Moving on toes in a circular manner in *Ardhamaṇḍala* is also described. The *sollukaṭṭu* of this *Aḍavu* is not given but the name of the *Aḍavu* itself points that *Sollukaṭṭu DigiDigi* can be used.

It is interesting to note that one of the Karnataka practicing traditions of *Bharatanāṭya*, the *Muguru Parampare*, has an *Aḍavu* called *Digi Digi Aḍavu*. This is done first moving in *Ardhamaṇḍala sthānaka* to the front on toes for the *Digidigidigidi* repeated six times and for *Thai* coming to rest with both feet in *Tattu*. The movement is again repeated going backwards. The *Aḍavu* has a variation in which the movement is done to the right side and back and left side and back using the same *Sthānakas* and leg movements.

7. *Digi digi Aḍavu: Kaiyādaḍavu*

Translation: *Digi digi Aḍavu* (it is called *Kaiyādaḍavu* by Tamilians). The verse starts by saying swaying hand, leg (most of the words in the two lines of text are missing with only the end word “*Matāha* meaning’ ‘it is opined’ is there. The verse also says that Example is *Digidigidigithai thaiyya*. The added note in the treatise

¹³ *Vicyava Bhūcāri* – One of the 16 earthly movements described in *Nāṭyaśāstra* which entails moving sideways on toes or by hitting the feet one after the other.

¹⁴ *Pādabedha* – Different types of leg movements. Five are mentioned in the treatise *Abhinaya Darpaṇa* by Nandikeshwara 1. Ten *Maṇḍala*-s (still poses) in which the first *Maṇḍala* called *Sthānaka* is further into six *Sthānakas* 2. Five *Utplavana Bhedas* (jumping or flying) 3. Seven *Bbramarīs* (twirling or going round) 4. Eight *Cāri Bhedas* (moving using the parts of the lower body such as waist, thigh, knees and feet) and finally 5. Ten *Gati Bhedas* (movements done imitating birds, animals and human beings)

says that certain types of hitting movements can be made based on different *Tālas* for *Digdigdigdigthai thaiyya*.

Analysis: Since most of the words are missing, the only clue here is the Tamilians calling it *Kaiyādaḍavu* and the *Sollukaṭṭu*, which is mentioned in the verse. *Sollukaṭṭu* resembles the *Bols*¹⁵ of *Tukadas*¹⁶ or *Thodas*¹⁷ of *Kathak*, which are short pieces of *Nṛtta*. *Digdigdigdigthai thaiyya* is done in *Kathak* going on the toes in *Samapāda*¹⁸ and moving fast the right foot and then left foot on toes one after the other twice, then taking *chakkar*¹⁹ twice and coming to rest in ‘*Sam*’ hitting the leg hard. The *Kaiyadaḍavu* might be pointing to an *Aḍavu* which was in vogue in the *Sadir* Nāṭch tradition using *Kathak bols*. Adaption of a *Kathak Tukuda* and *Bol* into *Sadir* repertoire is a possibility because dancers were moving from one king’s court to another displaying their talent and seeking reward as is written by the eminent writer Saskia C. Kersenboom in her book ‘*Nithyasumangail*’.

8. Utplutyotthānaṃ (*Kudicchu Elum-baradhu*)

Translation: Jumping up and standing on the ground with hands and feet spreading and making *Maṇḍala* as before (missing text) is marked as *Utplutyottānaṃ* (jumping and rising) *Thaitattttha* | *Thaitatddhittam* |

Analysis: In the description given above some of the key words are missing again, but a part of description and the name of the *Aḍavu*, *Utplutyottānaṃ* and also the Tamil words given *Kudicchu Elum-baradhu*, meaning jump and rise together is similar to *Plavana Aḍavu* done in present day repertoire. Dansuse Padma Subrahmanyam says – “Probably it is close to *Vidyutbhrāntā Ākasa Cāri*²⁰ (Subrahmanyam 2021:22)

¹⁵ *Bols* – Syllable which is said orally while dance is performed is a beat or a sound unit

¹⁶ *Tukdas* – They are short pieces of *Nṛtta* danced in *Kathak* for *Bols* in a particular *Tāla*

¹⁷ *Thodas* – They are bigger pieces of *Nṛtta* danced to more *Āvartas* of a *Tāla*. *Āvarta* is defined as when all the different parts in a *Tāla* such as *Laghu*, *Drta* and *Anudrta* are put once.

¹⁸ *Samapāda* – Standing straight with the heels and big toes touching each other

¹⁹ *Chakkar* – Taking a swirl and coming back to the starting position. This is akin to *Bhramarī Aḍavu*.

²⁰ *Vidyutbhrāntā Ākasa Cāri* – It is one of the 16 Aerial leg movement described in *Nāṭyaśāstra* which entails jumping with both the leg to the side and crossing one leg in front of the other when legs touch ground.

9. Text missing, no name given: (*Kudicchua Meṭṭu or Egari Meṭṭu*)

Translation: Here also differences are born based upon many features; jumping up and then pressing the heels on the ground (is that) which is called --- (missing text has half the name of the *Aḍavu* as *Yatplu*). ---- (missing text in the beginning of the next line) and then continues, which is called *Mardhana* by wisest of the knowledgeable in the *Naṭyaveda*. *Sollukaṭṭu* is *Taddhi thai thai Taddhi tam tam*.

Analysis: Whatever can be put together from the description in spite of the missing text in the verse is pointing towards *Kudicchua Meṭṭu or Egari Meṭṭu*. The key words which lead to this conclusion are *Yatplu*, *plu* in this might point to jumping up on toes and *Mardhana* which means forceful stamping or pressing the heels to the ground, which is done in *Kudicchu Meṭṭu*. What consolidates the *Aḍavu*'s identity is the Tamil name given in the treatise *Kudicchu Meṭṭu*.

10. *Sanatādyabhramanaṃ: (Bhramarī Aḍavu)*

Translation: Beating evenly lifting; as there is twirling by the right foot, so also by the left foot. If it is to be then it is called *Santādyabhramanaṃ*. *Sollukaṭṭu* is *Dhaidha*----(missing text)

Analysis: The description in the verse and the name *Bhramanaṃ* in the end of the *Aḍavu* points towards *Bhramarī Aḍavu* executed by taking a turn with one leg and then the other.

11. *Parṣṇikuṭṭanaṃ: (Taṭṭimeṭṭaḍavu)*

Translation: The beating by the right and left heels and hitting the whole sole on the ground. If there is an orderly manner in the beating then it would be named 'Parshnikuttana'. In Tamil it is written as *Taṭṭimeṭṭaḍavu*. *Sollu* is *Thaiyyataim Thaiyya thai*.

Analysis: The description given in the verse points to *Taṭṭimeṭṭaḍavu* and also there is a reference to the name in Tamil. But *Parṣṇikuṭṭana* is described a little differently from the way it is done today. The description says heels are hit first one after the other and then the whole sole is hit on the ground one after the other by the right and left legs, unlike today in most of the *Bānis* where the *kuṭṭana* is done by hitting the right sole to the ground and then lifting the heel half and hitting it to the

ground. Then toes of the left leg are hit lifting the heel, in the end hitting back the sole of the left leg. The leg movements of *Taṭṭi Meṭṭu* can vary a little from one *Bāni* to another.

12. *Mridusparśanasamjnakam: (Jāru or Sarikkal Aḍavu)*

Translation: On joining the left and right feet by their touching the ground in order in *Dṛta gati* (fast speed) that will be ‘*Mridusparśanasamjnakam*’ It is called *Anukkura aḍavu* in Tamil. *Sollu* is *Tadhithaim Tadhittamta*.

Analysis: From the explanation given it can be inferred *Mridusparśanasamjnakam* is done by joining the feet together by their touching the ground in fast speed. No other action is mentioned in the verse. The meaning of *Mridusparśana* is soft touch. If the movement described and name of the *Aḍavu* are put together, it points to joining one leg on the ground softly to the other leg in the third speed (*drita gati*). But what *Sthānaka* is used for joining is not clear. A sliding movement is indicated by the description in a fast manner. The only *Aḍavu* which meets this description is *Jāru* or *Sarikkal Aḍavu*.

The following has also been stated at this point in the treatise:

Translation: These (following) three can create many (more).

Analysis: This refers to the following three *Aḍavu-s*, namely, *Karṣana*, *Karṣanapādakam* and *Nāgabandham*, that can create many more *Aḍavu-s*.

13. *Karṣana: (Simir Aḍavu) Jāru Aḍavu or Sarikkal Aḍavu*

Translation: Adopting *Ardhmaḍala* pose with feet on the ground, if the right and left (foot) are drawn near then it is called *Karṣana*. In Tamil it is (called) *Simir Aḍavu*. *Sollu* is *Thaiyya Thai*.

Analysis: Description in the verse points towards *Jāru Aḍavu* or *Sarikkal Aḍavu* with the *sollukattu Tai ya Thai yi* which is used for the *Aḍavu* even today by many *Bānis*. The explanation given by Sarabhai (2000: 28) and Srinivasan Sudharani (1999: 157) have both described *Simir* as opening or expansive movement moving the hand away from the body which is done for most of the *Jāru Aḍavu-s* today.

14. *Karṣanapāḍakam*: (*Kadasakkāl*)

Translation: If, different categories of *Utpluthya* etc and if those categories were to be many; by dragging on either side on the ground by the feet and heels sequentially in *Drita* (fast) and other gaits the *Natya* experts call it '*Karṣanapadakaṃ*'. In Tamil it is (called) *Kadasakkāl*. *Sollu* is *Thai Thai Thai Thai*.

Analysis: The description points to a *Korvai Aḍavu* starting with a jump followed by sliding on soles or heels on both sides in fast pace. It could have been vogue during the time of the Treatise. The second part sliding fast on soles points to *Jāraḍavu* or *Sarikkal Aḍavu*.

15. A. *Swastika*: (*Taṭṭiktaṭṭḍavu*)

Translation: By the hand movements etc and if differences of these movements (variations) were to be many; the foot is beaten first and the thighs (a gap apart) are joined placing on the ground, front of the foot, that state is *Swastika*. *Taṭṭiktaṭṭḍavu*.

Analysis: The foot is hit and the thighs being joined with a gap between them indicates the hit foot being crossed by the other foot on its toes, the word given in the treatise is (*Pādāgre*) meaning on toes and the name given *Taṭṭiktaṭṭḍavu* reiterates this. The hand movements and many variations are done in this *Aḍavu* is true even today. All the eight bani-s active today do many variations of both hands and legs while doing *Taṭṭiktaṭṭḍavu*. It is known as *Tha Thai Thai Tha*, *Dhi Thai Thai Tha Aḍavu* today. The verse also points that even in the days of the treatise many variations were done in *Swastika Aḍavu*.

B. *Nagabandha*: (*Kartari Aḍavu*)

Translation: (Keeping the thigh in alignment by the (frontal) edges of the feet in the earlier tempo should be maintained that is called *Nagabandha*.

Analysis: It is mentioned that if the legs are crossed, in the front balancing on toes of both the legs maintaining the same tempo it is called *Nagabandha*. ***Kartari Aḍavu-s***, which are done today use the crossing of the legs in front with a jump.

It is also interesting to note that *Swastika* and *Nagabandha* given as *Aḍavu* in this treatise are mentioned as *Maṇḍala* and *Sthānaka* respectively under *Pādabheda* in

the Sanskrit Treatise *Abhinaya Darpaṇa* of Nandikesavara. These two are mentioned as *Dēśī Sthānakas* in the Treatise *Saṅgīta Ratnākara*. They are being mentioned as *Aḍavu-s* in *Saṅgīta Sārāmṛta*. There is no *Sollukaṭṭu* mentioned in the treatise for these two *Aḍavu-s*.

The first line of the verse is written as a note before explaining that the three *Aḍavu-s* *Karṣana*, *Kadasakkāl*, *Swastika* can create many more variations. This is very true, because each of these three *Aḍavu-s*, are done today with many variations in the way hands are moved, the *Hastas* are kept and the legs moved in many geometrical patterns. The three *Aḍavu-s* must have been done with many variations when the treatise was written.

16. *Saranagati*: (*Parikkira Aḍavu*)

Translation: Crawling by the feet forward and then to the sides after that a whirling movement, that is called *Saranagati* by name, in Tamil it is (called) *Parikkira Aḍavu*.

Analysis: Description of the *Aḍavu* points to crawling on all four limbs sideways and plucking oneself off from the ground taking a *Bhrahmarī* coming back to standing position. The meaning of *Parikki* in Tamil is to pluck, here after the crawling movement plucking oneself off from the ground is done by going on the knee and taking a turn in that position and coming back to *Samapāda* or *Āyata*. It is interesting to note that *Abhinaya Darpaṇa* mentions *Sarana* as one of the eight *Cāris* under *Pādabhedas*. No *Sollu* is given for this *Aḍavu*. In today's *Aḍavu* repertoire one of the variations of *Mandi Aḍavu* is done the way described in the treatise.

A Table comparing The *Aḍavu-s* in *Saṅgīta Sārāmṛta* with the Contemporary *Aḍavu-s* of *Bharatanāṭya* with the *Sollukaṭṭus* in the treatise and *Sollukaṭṭu* used in each *Bāni* for the *Aḍavu-s* is placed at Annexure 1. In the end.

Conclusion:

Many eminent writers have named and discussed the documentation of the *Aḍavu-s* mentioned in '*Saṅgīta Sārāmṛta*'. The translation from Sanskrit of the description of the *Aḍavu-s* and the detailed analysis to find out whether these descriptions in the treatise have

correlation to the contemporary *Aḍavu-s* was taken up by the Author of the paper which has yielded positive result.

The analysis definitely shows that 14 *Aḍavu-s* of Contemporary repertoire, have taken their root from the *Aḍavu-s* described in '*Saṅgīta Sārāmṛta*'. *Aḍavu* repertoire of *Sadir* having *Kathak bol* related *Aḍavu* is also proved by the Muguru repertoire having an *Aḍavu* which uses this bol and execution is similar to the way described in the Treatise. All the *Sollukaṭṭus* of *Aḍavu-s* in the treatise can be done in *Caturasra Eka Tāla* or *Ādi Tāla*. This practice is continued even today, since it is easier for beginners of dance to follow the four beats or eight beats. The study conclusively proves that Contemporary *Aḍavu-s* definitely go back in time to more than three hundred years. '*Saṅgīta Sārāmṛta*' of Tulajaji – I, is an invaluable treatise from the perspective of *Aḍavu-s*, since it is the only Treatise which has not only documented but described the method of executing the *Aḍavu-s*.

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Table - Annexure 1

3	<i>Parṣva-kuṭṭanam</i> (<i>Natti Thaṭṭu</i> <i>Adavu</i>) Thaiam Thathiyya	<i>Nattu</i> <i>aḍavu</i>	Tai Yum Dha Ta Tai Yum Da Ha	Thai Yum Tha Tha Thai Yam Tha Ha	Thai Yum Dath Tha Thai Yum Tha -m	Thai Yum Tha Tha Thai Yum Tha -m	Thai Ya Thai Ya Thai Ya Thai Tham	Tai Yum Ta Ta Tai - Ya -	Thai Yum That Tha Thai Yum Tha Ha	Tai Yum Ta Ta Tai Yum Tha -
4	<i>Pādapārsva-kuṭṭanam</i> (<i>Dhi Dhi Thai</i> <i>Aḍavu</i>) Dhi Dhi Tai	<i>Dhi Dhi</i> <i>Thai</i> <i>aḍavu</i>	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -
5	Padaparṣva-kuttana m Salaakai Sahita (<i>Dhi Dhi Thai</i> <i>Adavu wiyh hands</i>) Dhi Dhi Tai	<i>Dhi Dhi</i> <i>Thai</i> <i>with</i> <i>hands</i>	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -	Dhi Dhi Thai -
6	<i>Digidigiyadi-kuṭṭanam</i> Probable <i>Sollukaṭṭu</i> Digi Digi Digi Digi	No Equival ent not mention ed	Digdigdigdig Digdigdigdig Digdigdigdig Thai -	Not done	Not done	Not done	Not done	Not done	Not done	Not done
7	<i>Digi digi Aḍavu</i> (<i>Kai Yada adavu</i>) <i>Digdigdigdigthai</i> Thaiyya	No Equival ent not mention ed	Not done	Not done	Not done	Not done	Not done	Not done	Not done	Not done

8	<i>Utplutyothāanam</i> Thaitam Thaitham	<i>KudicchuElumbaradhu</i> (<i>Plavana</i>)	Ditha Languthaka ThadiginaThom-	Not Done	Thai Thai Thaam- Thai Thai Thaam-	Tha Thai Tham - Dhi Thai Tham -	Not done	Not done	Tha Thai Tham – Dhi Thai Tham -	Not Done
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*Aḍavu Name in Sanskrit, Tamil & Telugu with Sollukaṭṭu

	<i>Saṅgīta Sārāmṛta</i> *	Bharathanātya Aḍavus	<i>Bharathanātya Sollukaṭṭu</i>							
			Muguru	Mysore	Nanjanagudu	Kolar	Pandanallur	Tanjore	Vazhavor	Kalakshetra
9	Text missing, No name given Tadhi thai Tadhi Tam Tam	<i>KudicchuMeṭṭu</i> (<i>Egari Meṭṭu</i>)	Thai Ya Thai Yi	Thai Ha Thai Hi	Thai Hath Thai Hi	Thai Ha Thai Hi Thai Ha Tham -	Thai Ha Thai Hi	Tai Ta Tai Hi	Thai Hat Thai Ye	Thai Ha Thai Hi
10	<i>Sanatādy a-brama nam</i> Dhaidha a rest of	<i>Brahmarī Adavu</i>	Not Done	Thom Dhi Thom – Thai Dit Thai -	Thakadhi mi Thakajhanu Thakadhi	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done

	the sollukatt u missing				mi Thakajhan u					
11	<i>Parṣinik uttṭṭm (Taṭṭi Meṭṭu) Thaiyya taim Thaiyya Thai</i>	<i>Thaṭṭi Meṭṭu</i>	Tha Thai Thai Tam Dhi Thai Thai Tam	Tha Ka Dhi Mi Tha Ka Jha Nu	Tha Ka Dhi Mi Tha Ka Jha Nu	Not Done	Tha Ka Dhi Mi Tha Ka Jha Nu	Tha Ka Dhi Mi Tha Ka Jha Nu	Tha Ka Dhi Mi Tha Ka Jha Nu	Tha Ka Dhi Mi Tha Ka Jha Nu
12	<i>Mridusp arṣana-s amjnaka (Anukkur a Adavu)</i>	No Equivalent	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done
13	<i>Karṣṣna (Simir Aḍavu) Thaiyya Thaiyi</i>	<i>(Jāru or Sarikkal)</i>	Ta Tai Tai Ta Dhi Tai Tai Ta	Ta Tai Tai Ta Dhi Tai Tai Ta	Thai Hath Thai Hi/ Thaka Dhimi Thaka Jhanu	Thai Ha Thai Hi Thai Ha Thai Hi	Thai Hath Thai Hi	Tai Ya Tai Yi	Thai Yum Tha Tha Thai Yum Tha Ha	Thai Thai Tham – Dhi Thai Tham -
14	<i>Karṣṣna padakam (Kada-sh akkal)</i>	No Equivalent	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done

15a	<i>Swastika</i> (<i>Thaṭṭi</i> <i>Kaṭṭaḍavu</i> u back cross) No <i>Sollukaṭṭu</i>	Ta Tai Tai Tam Dhi Tai Tai Tam	Ta Tai Tai Tam Dhi Tai Tai Tam	Thathai Ditthai Thakka thai Kittathai	Thaka Dhimi Thaka Jhanu	Tha Thai Thai Tha Dit Thai Thai Tha				
15b	<i>Nagaban</i> <i>dha</i> (<i>Thaṭṭi</i> <i>Kaṭṭaḍavu</i> u front cross No <i>Sollukaṭṭu</i>	<i>Kartari Aḍavu</i>	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Dhi Thaim Dha Tha Thai – That Thaim Dha Tha Thai -
16	<i>Saranag</i> <i>ati</i> (<i>Parikka</i> <i>ra</i> <i>Aḍavu</i>) No <i>Sollukaṭṭu</i>	(<i>Mandi Korvai</i> <i>aḍavu</i>)	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Not Done	Thangida That That Dhinam

* *Aḍavu* Name in Sanskrit, Tamil & Telugu with *Sollukaṭṭu*